

From Dark Matter to Neutrinos: The Reach of Dual-Phase Xenon TPCs

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Liquid xenon detectors

- Leading sensitivity at intermediate/high DM masses since ~2007
- High mass number (argon $A=40$, xenon $A=131$) $\rightarrow \sigma \propto A^2$
- High stopping power \rightarrow self-shielding
- Non long-lived radioisotope \rightarrow background to ppt level
- Scalable to large target masses
- Simultaneous scintillation and ionization signal allows ER rejection
- Spin dependent interaction with odd isotopes (xenon)

Dual-phase TPC

- Measure scintillation light (S1) and ionisation signal (S2)
- 3D position reconstruction:
 - x-y from photosensor arrays
 - z from delay time between S1 and S2
- Electronic and nuclear recoil discrimination from S1/S2 ratio

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Current experiments

LZ (LUX-ZEPPELIN)

- Located at SURF, USA
- ~10 tonnes of LXe,
~7 tonnes active

XENONnT

- Located at LNGS, Italy
- ~8.5 tonnes of LXe,
~6 tonnes active

PandaX-4T

- Located at CJPL, China
- ~6 tonnes of LXe,
~4 tonnes active

Xenon TPC timeline

ZEPLIN-III /
XENON10

$\mathcal{O}(10 \text{ kg})$ LXe

$600 [\text{t d keV}]^{-1}$

2006

XENON100 /
PandaX-I / LUX

$\mathcal{O}(100 \text{ kg})$ LXe

$5.3 [\text{t d keV}]^{-1}$

~2010

PandaX-II /
XENON1T

$\mathcal{O}(1 \text{ t})$ LXe

$0.2 [\text{t d keV}]^{-1}$

2015

PandaX-4T /
XENONnT / LZ

$\mathcal{O}(10 \text{ t})$ LXe

$0.04 [\text{t d keV}]^{-1}$

2020s

XLZD / PandaX-xT

$\mathcal{O}(50 \text{ t})$ LXe

Reduce background
down to pp level

2030s

Radon removal

- Cryogenic distillation exploits difference in vapour pressure between Rn and Xe:
 - Continuous loop in XENONnT *Phys.Rev.X* 15 (2025) 3, 031079
 - Dedicated campaign in PandaX-4T
- Two operational modes: GXe-only and GXe+LXe
- Continuous GXe purification through heated zirconium in LZ
- Offline radon tagging
- 63% identification of ^{214}Pb decays

Eur. Phys. J. C (2017) 77:275

Eur. Phys. J. C (2022) 82:1104

arXiv: 2508.19117

WIMP scenario

Lower threshold
and detection
efficiency

Increase
exposure

CEνNS: coherent elastic
neutrino-nucleus scattering

- S2-only analyses / lower PMTs coincidence requirement from 3 to 2
- ML algorithms and data-driven constraints to mitigate accidental coincidences

- First steps to the MeV energy region with XENON1T → ADC saturation correction
- Sub % energy resolution at the ^{136}Xe double beta Q-value (~ 2458 keV) → Now reached $\sim 0.67\%$ in LZ

- Measurement of ^8B solar neutrinos through CE ν NS in XENONnT at 2.73σ and PandaX-4T at 2.64σ \rightarrow First CE ν NS measurement with Xe - last year
- Low energy deposit: $>90\%$ recoils below 2.1 keV
 - Lowering PMT coincidence threshold from 3 to 2 (XENON)
 - Analysis with S2-only signals (PandaX-4T)

- LZ measurement - last month $\rightarrow 4.5\sigma$ significance
- Measurement of SM weak mixing angle

Super-Kamiokande
50 kt

Mimic 6 GeV WIMP single scatter NR signal \rightarrow no discrimination

Kamland
1000 t

SNO
1000 t

Borexino
270 t

XENONnT
5.9 t

Figure by R. Hammann

- Dominant in neutrino flux → Search in electronic recoil below 250 keV
- Flux measured by PandaX-4T with commissioning run
- Achieved ^{222}Rn rate comparable with ER from solar pp neutrinos

Xe124 double weak decays

- 2ν ECEC of ^{124}Xe (abundance 0.095%) measured directly for the first time in XENON1T
 $\rightarrow T_{1/2} = (1.1 \pm 0.2_{\text{stat}} \pm 0.1_{\text{sys}}) \times 10^{22}$ yr
- Now a background for current generation experiments
- Several other double weak decays of ^{124}Xe under study: 0ν ECEC, $2\nu/0\nu\text{EC}\beta^+$, $2\nu/0\nu\beta^+\beta^+$
- Multi-site topology used to further reduce background

Nature 568 (2019) 7753, 532-535
Phys.Rev.C 106 (2022) 2, 024328

$2\nu\text{EC}\beta^+$ within reach:

$$\tau \sim 1.3 \times 10^{23} \text{ yr}$$

Eur.Phys.J.C 80 (2020) 12, 1161

Xe136 $0\nu\beta\beta$

- ^{136}Xe natural abundance of $\sim 8.9\%$ \rightarrow high exposure in ton-scale xenon TPCs
- Sensitivity affected by material background not-selected for MeV-range searches \rightarrow current experiment not yet competitive
- Proof of principle of the physics search (90% CL):
 - XENON1T $\rightarrow 36.16 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{yr}$ $T_{1/2}^{0\nu} > 1.2 \times 10^{24} \text{ yr}$
 - PandaX-4T $\rightarrow 44.6 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{yr}$ $T_{1/2}^{0\nu} > 2.1 \times 10^{24} \text{ yr}$
- Projected sensitivities (90% CL):
 - XENONnT $\rightarrow 275 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{yr}$ $T_{1/2}^{0\nu} > 2.1 \times 10^{25} \text{ yr}$
 - LZ $\rightarrow 1360 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{yr}$ $T_{1/2}^{0\nu} > 1.06 \times 10^{26} \text{ yr}$

Phys.Rev.C 106 (2022) 2, 024328
 Sci.Bull. 70 (2025) 1779-1785
 Phys.Rev.C 102 (2020) 1, 014602

Xe136/134 $2\nu\beta\beta$

- $2\nu\beta\beta \rightarrow$ half-life and shape analysis into the low energy region
- One of the main background at low energy for many physics processes
- PandaX-4T fit from 20 keV to 2800 keV:

$$T_{1/2}^{2\nu} = (2.14 \pm 0.05) \times 10^{21} \text{ yr}$$

Possible search also for $^{134}\text{Xe } 2\nu/0\nu\beta\beta$ (natural abundance $\sim 10.4\%$), never measured experimentally

- Q-value ~ 826 keV \rightarrow limited sensitivity for Xe136 enriched experiments
- PandaX-4T limit $\rightarrow T_{1/2}^{2\nu} > 2.8 \times 10^{22}$ yr
- LZ projected sensitivity $\rightarrow T_{1/2}^{2\nu} > 1.7 \times 10^{24}$ yr

The next-generation

- Current experiments $\mathcal{O}(10 \text{ t})$ LXe and 1.5 m dimensions, 1:1 ratio
- Next generation to increase SI-WIMP sensitivity by one order of magnitude $\sim 10^{-48} \text{ cm}^2 \rightarrow \sim 10^{-49} \text{ cm}^2$

XLZD and PandaX-xT

- WIMP search down to the neutrino floor
- Neutrino Physics
- Multi-channel observatory

Multi-purpose observatory

Eur.Phys.J.C 85 (2025) 10
J.Phys.G 52 (2025) 4, 045102
Sci.China Phys.Mech.Astron. 68 (2025) 2, 221011

Dark Matter

WIMPs
Sub-GeV
Inelastic
Axion-like particles
Planck mass
Dark photons

Neutrino nature

Neutrinoless double
beta decay
Neutrino magnetic
moment
Double electron
capture

Supernovae

Early alert
Supernova neutrinos
Multi-messenger
astrophysics

Sun

pp neutrinos
Solar metallicity
 ${}^7\text{Be}$, ${}^8\text{B}$, hep

WIMP search

- 90% exclusion sensitivity for SI cross section down to $2 \times 10^{-49} \text{ cm}^2$ at 40 GeV mass for ~ 200 tonnes \times year exposure
- 3σ discovery at $7 \times 10^{-49} \text{ cm}^2$ for ~ 200 tonnes \times year and $3 \times 10^{-49} \text{ cm}^2$ for ~ 1000 tonnes \times year exposure

- 90% exclusion sensitivity for SI cross section down to $3.5 \times 10^{-49} \text{ cm}^2$ at 40 GeV mass for ~ 200 tonnes \times year exposure

- 60 t LXe active target → up to 80 t depending on xenon supply market
- Two arrays of photosensors → baseline design with ~2400 3" PMTs
- Double-walled low-background Ti cryostat + LXe instrumented around the TPC
- Gadolinium loaded water tank to enhance neutron capture cross-section

Sci.China Phys.Mech.Astron. 68 (2025) 2, 221011

- ~43 t LXe active target
- Two arrays of photosensors → ~8000 2" square PMTs
- Thin ultra pure Cu inner vessel + double-walled low-background Ti cryostat with instrumented liquid scintillator in between
- Water tank with passive ultrapure water veto +5% WbLS at later stage

Challenges

- Scaling up infrastructures
- High-voltage delivery:
 - Electrodes and HV feedthrough design
 - Electric field homogeneity
- Liquid xenon purity
- Background mitigation
- Light collection efficiency
- Photosensors performance

JINST 16, P08052 (2021)
Eur. Phys. J. C 83, 717 (2023)
JINST 20, P04013 (2025)

JINST 19 (2024) P05018

- Photosensors:
 - Radiopurity improvement on 3" PMTs
 - Testing of Square 2" PMTs → lower buoyancy and sub-ns rise time
 - Testing of 12x12 mm² MPPC of VUV4 SiPMs → low-radioactivity, cheap but higher dark count rate
 - Other photosensors under study (digital SiPM, hybrid sensors,...)
- HV and grids - design, production, quality testing and repair of electrodes:
 - Stretching, sagging and flatness of meshes
 - Diagnostic of defects and reparation with laser welding
 - Electrode surface treatment and coating
 - Study electron and photon emission

Background mitigation

- ^{85}Kr distillation \rightarrow goal of 0.1 ppt $^{\text{nat}}\text{Kr}$ already achieved <0.026 ppt
- ^{222}Rn distillation column \rightarrow goal of 0.1 $\mu\text{Bq}/\text{kg}$ (achieved 0.8 $\mu\text{Bq}/\text{kg}$) below ER from solar pp neutrinos
- Coating techniques against radon emanation (electrochemical deposition of Cu)
- Fast recirculation in liquid to reduce impurities, with radon-free filters and pumps
- Radio-pure materials with low Rn-emanation
- Software radon-background reduction techniques

Solar neutrinos

- Nuclear and electronic recoil signatures
- Expected $\mathcal{O}(10)$ events/t/yr of ^8B CEvNS in XLZD and PandaX-xT
- Aims to measure pp solar neutrino spectrum
- Constrain low-energy survival probability to 3-5%
- Independent measurement of the weak mixing angle

Sci.China Phys.Mech.Astron. 68 (2025) 2, 221011

SNO 2013

B16-GS98 (HZ)

B16-AGSS09met (LZ)

PandaX-30T 200 tonne-year

Eur.Phys.JC 85 (2025) 10

Xe136 $0\nu\beta\beta$

- ^{136}Xe natural abundance of 8.9%
- Competitive with next generation of dedicated $0\nu\beta\beta$ xenon experiments
- Covering the full inverted ordering

J.Phys.G 52 (2025) 4, 045102

Core collapse supernova

- Neutrino emission from core collapse supernova detected through CEvNS
- Sensitivity to all neutrino flavours \rightarrow few events/ton expected from SN at ~ 10 kpc
- Signal highly concentrated in time, ~ 10 s
- Early-alert system network - XLZD will be part of SNEWS2.0

Conclusion and outlook

- Dual phase xenon TPC leading the WIMP searches
- Technology feasible for different neutrino physics channels
 - First measurement of ^{124}Xe $2\nu\text{ECEC}$
 - Measurements of solar neutrinos through CEvNS (^8B and pp)
 - Spectral shape and half-life of $2\nu\beta\beta/0\nu\beta\beta$
- Planned next generation experiments to reach the neutrino floor
- Rich physics landscape from dark matter to neutrino physics

Contributions at NuPhys

- Andrew Stevens - *Latest results from XENONnT and prospects for the future*
- Albert Baker - *Recent results from the LUX-ZEPLIN experiment*
- Yongheng Xu - *Probing solar neutrino properties with the LUX-ZEPLIN experiment*
- Yang Zhang - *Astro-neutrino detection at PandaX-4T*
- Jim Dobson - *Radiopurity and cleanliness challenges for the XLZD experiment*
- Jim Dobson (Ricardo Peres) - *Neutrino physics with XLZD*

Thank you!

Backups

Detection by scattering of WIMP off target nucleus → nuclear recoil signature

$$\frac{dR}{dE_{nr}} = \frac{M_T}{m_N} \frac{\rho_0}{m_\chi} \int_{v_{min}}^{v_{esc}} \epsilon(E_{nr}) v \cdot f(\vec{v}) \frac{d\sigma_{\chi, N}}{dE_{nr}} dv$$

Astrophysical inputs:

- Local DM density near the Sun: $\rho_0 \simeq 0.3 \text{ GeV cm}^{-3}$
- WIMP velocity distribution $f(v)$ assumed to follow Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution → depends on the circular velocity around the galactic center:
 $v(r_{sun}) \simeq 220 \text{ km/s}$
- Escape velocity: $v_{esc} \simeq 544 \text{ km/s}$

Particle physics:

- DM-nucleon scattering cross section $\sigma_{\chi, N}$
- Assumed low momentum transfer
- Spin-independent scattering usually assumed: $\sigma_0^{SI} \propto A^2$

Detector physics:

- Target material: atomic mass m_N and total mass M_T
- Energy threshold v_{min} and detection efficiency $\epsilon(E_{nr})$

XENONnT radon removal system

Eur.Phys.J.C 82 (2022) 12, 1104

- Two operational modes: GXe-only and GXe+LXe
- Cryogenic distillation exploits difference in vapour pressure between Rn and Xe
- Radon trapped in reboiler's LXe until decay
- Extract radon-depleted GXe from the top condenser
- Required development of radon-free compressor and heat exchangers

Argon TPCs for DM

- Same working principle as xenon TPCs - with SiPMs photodetectors
- Global effort merging into DarkSide-20k (DEAP-3600, ArDM, DarkSide-50, MiniCLEAN)
- DarkSide-20k under construction → similar sensitivity of LZ, XENONnT, PandaX-4T
- ^{39}Ar cosmogenic intrinsic background at low energy → argon purified in ~350 m high cryogenic distillation column (Aria) in Sardinia

